

STUDY OF GOVERNMENT POLICY AND CULTURE DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON MARKET RESPONSE

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Abstract

This study explores the market reaction during the pandemic and its impact on market returns related to government policies such as state lockdowns, stimulus policies, travel bans, and monetary policies as well as the national culture of countries infected with COVID-19. In this study, the methodology used a literature review approach to market response during the COVID-19 period. The results of this study indicate that the average abnormal returns at the market level reported from 25 countries only 11 countries on the day the stimulus package was implemented had a statistically significant negative effect on returns and only three countries had a statistically significant positive effect on returns. State lockouts have a negative effect on stock returns in only 10 countries out of 25 countries and only two country locks have a statistically significant positive effect on returns. Travel bans have a significant positive effect on returns in five countries and there are three countries statistically, where travel bans have a significant negative effect. There were changes in monetary policy in 13 countries on the day the first changes in cash exchange rates were announced. Market returns in three countries experienced increasing returns while only two countries experienced decreasing returns. Stock markets reacted more negatively to countries with low individualism and high uncertainty aversion up to three weeks after the first announcement of COVID-19 infections in those countries.

Keywords: COVID-19, government policy, market returns, culture

JEL Codes: I18

1. Introduction

The outbreak of Corona virus Diseases 19 (COVID-19) is an infectious disease that first appeared in China in December 2019 and received great attention from media coverage around the world (Haroon & Rizvi, 2020). COVID-19 continues to spread to other countries causing a negative impact on global financial markets (Haroon & Rizvi, 2020; Karamti & Belhassine, 2022). Investors reacted to a pandemic when it was first detected in their country, and is the reaction in one country different from another because of differences in their national culture? (Fernandez-perez et al., 2021). (Ru et al., 2020) documented that countries with Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) experiences reacted with faster and sharper declines in market prices, while (Hassan et al., 2020) shows that companies with SARS experiences were more positive in their ability to deal with COVID-19.

Research by (Fernandez-perez et al., 2021) measures the extent to which societies are tolerant of uncertain outcomes. Countries with high individualism scores experienced smaller stock

market declines than countries with low individualism scores at the end of the third week since the announcement of the first infection and countries with higher uncertainty avoidance scores showed larger stock market declines than did countries with higher individualism scores. Countries with lower uncertainty aversion over the same period.

On the other hand (Bannigidmath et al., 2021) evaluates stock market responses in 25 countries related to government policies during the COVID-19 pandemic by considering four specific policies, namely state lockdowns, stimulus packages, travel bans, and monetary policies. However, the impact of government policies on the stock market remains unclear. On the one hand, if investors welcome the government's actions, they will adjust their return expectations less negatively. On the other hand, if investors perceive politicians as selfish or the government is overreacting, they will react more negatively (Ashraf, 2020).

This study tries to discuss previous articles related to the stock market and financial response during the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Pandemic COVID-19

COVID-19 became the world's attention in December 2019 since the virus was first discovered in Wuhan (China). The rapid spread of the virus and the increasing number of confirmed cases made the Chinese government take action by locking the entire city of Wuhan on January 23, 2020, as an isolation measure. One week later, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the outbreak in China a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) with the total number of confirmed cases being 7,711 and only 83 cases in 18 countries outside China (Zhang et al., 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic is causing a worldwide crisis, where COVID-19 is like a "once in a century pathogen" (Gates, 2020). With its spread so rapidly with its scale and trajectory that the WHO declared COVID-19 first a global emergency on 20 February 2020, and then a pandemic on 11 March 2020 (Ali et al., 2020). COVID-19 is expected to have a much bigger impact on the global economy (Zhang et al., 2020).

2.2. Government Policy and Culture

COVID-19 is an event that shocked the world which has made governments around the world take different views and actions about the impact of COVID-19 on their countries. Some countries implement emergency policies in the form of state locks that restrict human movement. The state lockdown is a government measure to be able to control the COVID-19 virus so that the country can quickly escape the pandemic and have no impact on the financial and stock markets. Other policies from the government against the COVID-19 pandemic are social distancing, travel bans, health testing and quarantine, fiscal stimulus, monetary policy, and economic packages (Ashraf, 2020; Bannigidmath et al., 2021).

Government policies aim to reduce or break the chain of disease spread. However, this policy caused many negative impacts in some business sectors such as the tourism, hotel, and restaurant sectors. (Nasution et al., 2021 and Warae et al., 2021). However, on the other hand,

it has a positive impact on some business sectors such as the health and pharmaceutical sectors. The government's policies related to the COVID-19 pandemic have triggered market reactions and created market uncertainty and created panic among investors in the stock and financial markets.

The cultural dimension explains how investors respond during the crisis period to avoid uncertainty about COVID-19 based on behavioral factors such as fear and ignorance (Fernandez-perez et al., 2021). Overreaction to uncertainties in times of crisis such as COVID-19 led to larger market declines and resulted in a drop in stock prices far exceeding the targeted growth slowdown thus implying that other factors such as a shift in risk aversion had an impact on the market reaction (Gormsen, 2020). COVID-19 provides an opportunity to explore how cross-country differences such as culture impact the initial reaction to a disaster (Fernandez-perez et al., 2021).

3. Methods

This research design uses a literature review approach to market response during the COVID-19 period. The methodology is carried out with a brief review of several previous studies so that it can be concluded briefly and in detail without testing the data. We try to discuss the methodology from the existing literature (Bannigidadmth et al., 2021; Fernandez-perez et al., 2021).

(Bannigidadmth et al., 2021) examines the impact of COVID-19 events on the return performance of the benchmark equity index of 25 countries in which each country, begins by calculating daily returns for all firms in our sample. The abnormal returns are computed using both the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) and (Fama & French, 1993) three-factor models, which the following regression:

$$R_{i,j,t} = \hat{\alpha}_{i,j} + \hat{\beta}_{i,j}(R_{m,j,t} - R_{f,j,t}) + \hat{\sigma}_{mbi,j}SMB_t + \hat{\sigma}_{hmlj,j}HML_t \quad (1)$$

where $R_{i,j,t}$ is the excess return of firm i from country j on day t ; $R_{f,j,t}$ is country j 's risk-free rate; $R_{m,j,t}$ is the weighted value of the benchmark return index of country j ; SMB_t is a size factor calculated as the market capitalization of small-minus-large companies; and HML_t is the value factor calculated as a high-minus-low book-to-market company. The model is estimated using the estimation period 01/02/2019 – 31/10/2019. Using the usual least squares estimates $\hat{\alpha}_i$, $\hat{\beta}_i$, $\hat{\sigma}_{mbi}$, dan $\hat{\sigma}_{hmlj}$ from equation (1), the Abnormal Return (AR) for each firm i of country j on day t is calculated as:

$$AR_{i,j,t} = R_{i,j,t} - \hat{\alpha}_{i,j} - \hat{\beta}_{i,j}(R_{m,j,t} - R_{f,j,t}) - \hat{\sigma}_{mbi,j}SMB_t - \hat{\sigma}_{hmlj,j}HML_t \quad (2)$$

The average abnormal return (AAR_{jt}) at the market level for each country on the day of the event is calculated by means of the cross-sectional AR of all firms in the market aggregate. A cross-sectional approach is commonly used for significance testing. Cumulative Average Abnormal Returns (CAAR_s) dan average buy-hold abnormal returns (BHAR), which the following regression:

$$CAAR_{j,T1,T2} = \sum_{t=T1}^T AAR_{jt} \quad (3)$$

$$BHAR_{ij,T1,T2} = \prod_{t=T1}^{T2} (1 + R_{ijt}) - \prod_{t=T1}^{T2} [1 + E(R_{ijt})] \quad (4)$$

Then in the research conducted (Fernandez-perez et al., 2021) examine the stock market response in terms of cumulative abnormal stock market return (CAR) or abnormal stock market return volatility (AVOLA) by calculating the abnormal stock market return by subtracting the logarithmic return of the stock market on day t by the average daily logarithmic return in country i. The following regression model is used to examine the influence of culture on the stock market response around the official confirmation of the first infected case across countries:

$$RESPONSE_i = \alpha + \beta CULTURE_i + \gamma_1 \ln(GDPPC)_i + \gamma_2 \ln(DENS)_i + \gamma_3 \ln(CCASE)_i + \gamma_4 VIX_i + \gamma_5 GDPGRW_i + \epsilon_i$$

Where RESPONSE_i is either CAR or AVOLA for country i, and CULTURE is either culture indexes of individualism (IDV) or uncertainty avoidance (UAI). Then several country-specific factors such as the total value of gross domestic products per capita (GDPPC) are controlled as a proxy for a country's economic wealth, and population density per square kilometer (DENS) untuk menangkap potensi penyebaran COVID-19 dalam negara. To control for this, (Fernandez-perez et al., 2021) includes the cumulative infected cases (CCASE) n all countries globally as well as the Chicago Board of Exchange (CBOE) market volatility (VIX), which is widely used in the literature (Baker & Wurgler, 2007; Da et al., 2015; Whaley, 2000) on market sentiment and investor fear. Both CCASE and VIX were acquired on the date of the first infected case in a country.

4. Result and Discussion

(Bannigidadmth et al., 2021) conducted a study in the period 2 January 2019 to 31 August 2020 on the top 25 countries that have an influence on COVID-19 in terms of the number of infected cases and deaths. Meanwhile, the average abnormal returns at the market level were reported from 25 countries, only 11 countries on the day the stimulus package was implemented had a statistically significant negative effect on returns and only three countries had a statistically significant positive effect on returns. On the other hand, state lockouts have

a negative effect on stock returns in only 10 countries out of 25 countries and only two country locks have a statistically significant positive effect on returns. Other policies such as travel bans have a significant positive effect on returns in five countries and there are three countries statistically that travel bans have a significant negative effect.

On the other hand (Bannigidadmth et al., 2021) analyzes the cumulative effect over the five days following the event. The results of the analysis of state lockouts there are 14 countries that have a statistically significant effect on returns. The five-day cumulative effect of the stimulus package in 11 countries had a significant negative effect but only three countries had a positive effect. Next, the five-day cumulative effect of travel bans in three countries has a significant positive effect on returns while seven countries have a significant negative effect on returns.

Monetary policy affects returns on research (Bannigidadmth et al., 2021). There were changes in monetary policy in 13 countries on the day the first changes in cash exchange rates were announced. Market returns in three countries experienced increasing returns while only two countries experienced decreasing returns. Furthermore, the cumulative effect over the five days following the event experienced a decrease in returns in six countries and only five countries experienced an increase in returns.

(Fernandez-perez et al., 2021) stated that overall shows the stock market react more negatively in countries with low individualism and high uncertainty aversion up to three weeks after the first announcement of COVID-19 infections in those countries. These results are strong given the presence of global fears among investors and the influence of fundamentals. Then also the volatility of daily stock market returns is higher for countries with lower individualism and higher uncertainty aversion during the first three weeks after the first announcement of COVID-19 infections in those countries.

5. Conclusion

COVID-19 has a different effect on returns in each country related to the policies taken by the government. Countries with low individualism and high uncertainty aversion show a negative stock market reaction.

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